

Design and analysis of silicon photonic switch matrix for reconfigurable electronic-photonic integrated circuits

Madhupriya G*, Indhumathi R

Centre for Nonlinear Science and Engineering (CeNSE),
School of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, SASTRA Deemed University,
Thanjavur-613401, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract—In this article a silicon photonic switch matrix (PSM) is designed for reconfigurable electronic-photonic integrated circuits (RePIC), which includes the 1x1 ON-OFF silicon photonic switch and a tunable directional coupler (TDC). The proposed PSM routes the incoming four light signals in all the possible directions with the help of six 1x1 ON-OFF switches and a TDC. The control of the ON-OFF switch and the tunable directional couplers are performed using the forward-biased PIN junction configuration utilizing the plasma dispersion effect, where the change in refractive index is obtained by altering the carrier concentration with the external electric field. The individual components are designed using the beam propagation method (BPM) and the transmission characteristics are converted into a compact numerical model (CNM) and are utilized in a block-based circuit design approach for large-scale photonic integrated circuits. This provides flexibility in expressing large-scaled photonic circuits without performing the physically-based electromagnetic simulation.

Index Terms—silicon photonics, reconfigurable electronic-photonic integrated circuit, photonic switch matrix, reconfigurable directional coupler.

I. Introduction

The research on photonic integrated circuits has emerged from the last decades, which integrates active and passive photonic components in a monolithic or heterogeneous way on a single chip. The photonic IC platforms such as SoI, SiN, InP, and LNOI are being developed to an industrial scale [1, 2]. Further, the heterogeneous integration of lithium niobate (LN) with SoI waveguides has attracted significant interest, which enabled electro-optical tunable resonators, Mach-Zehnder modulators, and Mid-IR modulators. The industry ready silicon platform such as SoI follows a zero-change CMOS fabrication process to fabricate the silicon photonic components.

II. Design of photonic switch matrix

The proposed photonic switch works based on the ON-OFF switching mechanism using a 1x1 directional coupler. This can be viewed with a traditional 2x2 directional coupler with a waveguide that is internally terminated. The architecture view of the 1x1 ON-OFF photonic switch is shown in Fig.1(a). During the absence of an external

electric field, the incoming light takes the cross-state operation and the maximum light intensity is absorbed with the help of termination block [1,2], and a very minimum, negligible amount of intensity will be available at the access waveguide, this state of operation is considered as OFF-state. With an external electric field, the incoming light traverses in the same waveguide without coupling to the adjacent waveguide, hence a maximum amount of intensity will be available at the end of the access waveguide. This state of operation is known as ON-state [3]. The input-output electric field relations in terms of field-coupling coefficient (κ) is derived as follows [4]. The electric field of the light at the output port (E_o) is expressed using equations (1) and (2), in which the equation (2) acts as the characteristic equation for the 1x1 ON-OFF photonic switch.

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_{o1} \\ E_{o2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{1 - \kappa(V)} & j\sqrt{\kappa(V)} \\ j\sqrt{\kappa(V)} & \sqrt{1 - \kappa(V)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E_{i1} \\ E_{i2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$E_o = \sqrt{1 - \kappa(V)} E \quad (2)$$

where, E_{o1} , E_{o2} represents the output electric fields of the input lights, E_{i1} , E_{i2} are the electric fields of the input lights, κ is the cross field-coupling factor, and $\kappa(V)$ represents the voltage-controlled field-coupling factor, which is obtained by forward biased PIN configuration [1,4]. The value of the field-coupling factor decides the ON-state, tunable-state, and OFF-state operation. The maximum value field-coupling coefficient ($\kappa \approx 1$), leads to maximum coupling to the terminal block, and the minimum value ($\kappa \approx 0$) results in the transmission of the input light to the output port.

The proposed reconfigurable switch matrix is shown in Fig.1 (b), where it includes 6-number of 1x1 switches (S1 to S6) and a tunable directional coupler. Based on the developed compact numerical model of 1x1 photonic switch, and the tunable directional coupler the photonic switch matrix is constructed [4,5].

III. Results and discussion

The light signal available at port-A and port-C can simultaneously be routed to port-B and port-D respectively, and its transmission characteristics are shown in

*Corresponding author: madhupriyaganesh019@gmail.com

Fig. 1. The schematic representation of (a). 1×1 silicon photonic switch.

Fig. 2. The proposed reconfigurable photonic switch matrix.

Fig.2 (a). To establish path A to B, switches S1, S4 should be maintained in OFF-state, switch S5 should be maintained in the ON-state, and the tunable directional coupler (TDC) should be maintained in the cross-state. At the same time, to establish the path from C to D, switch S3 should be maintained in OFF-state, switch S6 should be maintained in ON-state, and the TDC is already configured in cross-state. The input lights at port-A and port-C take cross-state propagation in TDC and propagate to the respective output ports port-B and port-D. The incoming light at port-A is routed to port-D via switch S1, at the same time the switches S4 and S5 are maintained in OFF-state to avoid the interference due to light at the port-C is illustrated in Fig.2 (b). Similarly, the routing paths from A to C is established. In the same way, the routing paths from C to B is established by maintaining the switch S3 in ON-state the switch S6 in

OFF-state. Similarly, the path B to Dis established.

Fig. 3. Simulation results for the bar-state configuration (A to B, C to D) routing.

Fig. 4. Simulation results for the cross-state configuration (A to D, B to C) routing.

IV. Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed a reconfigurable photonic switch matrix and numerically demonstrated using two 1×1 photonic switches and a tunable directional coupler. The designed 1×1 photonic switch shows an ON-state insertion loss of 0.02 dB at 0.951 V and an OFF-state loss of -11.04 dB at 0 V. The same geometrical dimensions were adopted for the tunable directional coupler, that exhibits only bar-and cross-state operation. Numerical simulations confirming the photonic switch matrix and various figures of merit are calculated from the simulation results. In conclusion, based on the optimum performance, the photonic switch matrix can be used for the reconfigurable photonic integrated circuits.

References

- [1] M.A.Meerasha, T.S. Meetei, G. Madhupriya et al. J Comput Electron 2020, 19, 1651.
- [2] M. A. Meerasha, and K. Pandiyan Electronics Letters, 2020, 56, 1130
- [3] Daniel Pérez-López, Ana M. Gutierrez, Erica Sánchez, et al.Opt. Express2019, 27, 38071.
- [4] Bogaerts, Wim, Daniel Pérez, José Capmany, et al.Nature2020, 586, 207.
- [5] Lu, Zeqin, Han Yun, Yun Wang, et al. Optics express2015, 23, 3795.